

Laser Line Triangulation Sensor with Wide Measurement Range: a Steel Industry Use Case

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Abstract — Laser line triangulation is a key measurement technology that can be applied in quality control processes to inspect product geometry without contact. This paper presents the design of a Laser Line Triangulation (LLT) sensor developed in the context of the Horizon Europe (HE) project openZDM and tested inline in a steel industry use case.

The LLT sensor has been developed focusing on two main target objectives: wide measurement range along transversal (X) and axial (Z) directions and small resolution along the Z axis. These have been achieved thanks to the optimization of the design parameters of the system which has been implemented with a triangulation angle of 45° reaching over a stand-off distance of 1000 mm and a 1000 mm camera-laser distance. The overall measurement range results in a transversal Field-Of-View (X-FOV) from 800 mm to 2000 mm and a minimum Z distance of 630 mm in the near field up to 1580 mm in the far field.

The resolution along the Z axis has been enhanced thanks to the introduction of subpixel accuracy reaching 0.026 mm at the stand-off distance which is 1000 mm. In this paper, these values are compared to other Laser Line Triangulation sensors available on the market showing that the system developed by UNIVPM is innovative.

The Laser Line Triangulation sensor has been also tested inline and this paper presents some results of the laser profiles acquired on a steel bar held by a robot. These laser profiles are then processed in order to detect geometric defects, in particular the non-straightness of the bar, using an algorithm properly developed for the use case. From the results of these feasibility tests, the application has proven effective and opens the path to a full-inline installation, in order to measure non-straightness on 100% of the products.

Keywords — Zero-defect manufacturing, non-destructive inspection, Industry 4.0, steel industry, in-line quality control, straightness, laser triangulation sensor, resolution, feature extraction

I. INTRODUCTION

Zero Defect Manufacturing (ZDM) is becoming more and more attractive for companies as it considerably reduces the costs related to the treatment of defective products [1]. Moreover, the ZDM approach increases also customer's satisfaction which is a core benefit for the company.

Targeting the ZDM approach, UNIVPM is developing in collaboration with other partners of the openZDM project, a Laser Line Triangulation (LLT) sensor which will be installed

in VDL Weweler B.V. production line, in a steel processing plant producing trailing arms.

This paper presents in Chapter II the context of the HE project openZDM where the Laser Line Triangulation sensor is developed and deployed in one pilot use case. The pilot sets the specifications for the laser line system, presented in Section II-B, which are taken into account in the design phase. In Chapter III the main features of the Laser Line Triangulation sensor are presented, focusing on measurement range and resolution along Z axis. Moreover, the measurement setup for the feasibility tests performed inline is described, along with the setting of the optical parameters and the acquisition parameters. In Chapter IV the results of the inline acquisition are presented and finally Chapter V reports the conclusions and next steps.

II. OPENZDM FRAMEWORK

A. Laser Line Triangulation sensors for geometry measurement: VDL Weweler B.V. use case

In the context of the Horizon Europe project openZDM [2] several non-destructive inspection techniques are developed in order to perform quality assessment in five pilot manufacturing industries. This paper targets the pilot manufacturing industry VDL Weweler B.V., located in Apeldoorn (NL), which develops, produces, tests, and sells air suspension systems, axle lift systems and parabolic springs [3]. As non-destructive inspection technique, this paper presents the laser line triangulation which is widely used for dimensional measurements. In the use case, the LLT technique is used to evaluate the straightness of steel bars in the pilot manufacturing industry process which produces trailing arms.

The steel bar to be inspected has an overall wide length dimension (up to 1000 mm or more) which can pose limits if using standard quality testing techniques such as coordinate measuring machines or tactile sensors. Therefore, a non-contact technology, like laser line triangulation, proves to be suitable for this use case, allowing short measuring times and an increase in information density [4].

B. Requirements and specifications for Laser Line Triangulation Sensor

The Laser Line Triangulation sensor will inspect the steel bar at two different stages of the production process, the first at a low temperature and the second when the bar is heated up to 1200 °C.

The goal is to inspect the product and find defects at an early stage of the process, in order to prevent them from evolving along the production line. In this way there are also cost and material savings as it is avoided to use energy and material on a product that will become scrap.

Different type of steel bars have to be inspected with average dimensions: length 650-1000 mm, thickness of 50-60 mm, and width 90-100 mm.

The parameter to be measured is the straightness of the bar which is defined as the deviation from a straight line. It can be observed in the plane Z-X, referencing the cartesian reference system in Figure II-1. Tolerance on straightness is specified as 0,2% of bar length; whenever deviations of the straightness over width $\Delta Z / \Delta X$ (on the Z-X plane) is in the order of 1-2 mm/m or more, the bar is considered non-straight, therefore it is a defect.

Figure II-1 Requirement definition for defect of non-straightness

This implies that, for conformity assessment, the measuring system needs to be able to detect non-straightness with an uncertainty lower than 0,2 mm (10% of max tolerance) [5].

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Laser Line Triangulation sensor design

The Laser Line Triangulation sensor developed by UNIVPM features a wide measurement range which is peculiar for Laser Line Triangulation systems that usually deal with much smaller measurement ranges. The system measurement range has been defined considering that the steel bar can reach a length of 1000 mm.

The system parameters chosen for this application, which result in the optimal compromise for resolution along Z axis and overall dimensions of the system [6] are:

- X-FOV: 1200 mm
- Angle of triangulation: 45°
- Stand-off distance: 1000 mm

This implies a base distance of 1000 mm between camera and laser. The configuration chosen features the laser perpendicular to the object and the camera inclined at the angle of triangulation.

With this system parameters chosen, the measurement range of the sensor is quite large (see Figure III-1) from X-FOV of 800 mm in the near field (at Z=630 mm) to 2000 mm in the far field (at Z=1580 mm) with a X-FOV of 1200 mm at the stand-off distance Z=1000 mm.

Figure III-2 shows a comparison of the measurement range with that of large range LLT sensors available on the market

[7] [8]. LLT sensors in general have a trapezoidal shaped measurement range, the LLT sensor presented in this paper shows the smallest ratio of trapezoid height to base width, compared to the other reported in Figure III-2. This is done to improve resolution over Z, as required from the specifications for bar straightness measurement.

Figure III-1 LLT sensor measurement range

Furthermore, it is possible to notice that, even though other systems with large measurement range exist, the X-FOV is still limited to 1200 mm and, in the overall Z-range, the X-FOV changes a lot, not allowing to measure a long product at different distances. On the other hand, the Laser Line Triangulation sensor developed by UNIVPM allows to measure long products (more than 1000 mm) from 800 mm to 1600 mm distance, allowing high flexibility in the choice of the product positioning. Moreover, the LLT sensor developed by UNIVPM features just one camera, differentiating from others on the market that exploit two cameras and one laser projector as a method to enhance FOV [8].

Figure III-2 Comparison of LLT sensors measurement range

The resolution along Z axis of the sensor is not constant along the Z direction and depends on different factors. An influencing one is the camera spatial resolution, which, for this use case, is AT C5-2040-GigE smart camera with 2048x1088 pixels and a pixel size of 5.5 μm . The camera optics is KOWA Lens model LM12HC with focal length 12.5 mm.

Given the technical data of the sensor and the overall system geometry, the resolution along Z axis has been computed obtaining the curve in blue (see Figure III-4) [6].

The resolution along the Z axis is computed considering the difference obtained in the laser plane of the Z coordinate, moving the i coordinate along the lines of the sensor, from 1

to 1088 which is the number of pixels in the vertical direction of the sensor (see Figure III-3).

Figure III-3 Laser Line Triangulation sensor geometry for resolution along Z-axis definition

The formulas used in order to compute the resolution along the Z axis are reported in (1), given the parameters definition of Figure III-3:

$$\begin{cases} z_i = d * \tan(\varphi_i + \beta) - SO \\ \Delta z = z_{i+1} - z_i \\ i = 1 : n \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The value measured in the Z-scale can be enhanced using subpixel accuracy which, with the C5 series camera, is calculated using the following formula (2):

$$Z - \text{Scale} = \frac{1}{2 \text{SubpixelValue}} \quad (2)$$

The Subpixel value for the C5 Series camera can vary from 1 up to 6.

Using a Subpixel Value of 5, the resolution along Z axis can be optimized reaching a value of 0.026 mm at the stand-off distance.

Using subpixel accuracy, the resolution along Z axis values meet the requirements of the use case which is to detect non-straightness deviation of the order of 1-2 mm, resolving minimum values down to 0.1-0.2 mm [6].

Figure III-4 Resolution along Z axis of the LLT sensor

Comparing the resolution along Z axis values of the Laser Line Triangulation system developed by UNIVPM and the other sensors available on the market and previously considered (values in Table 1), it is shown that, if using subpixel accuracy the UNIVPM sensor is really competitive.

Table 1 - Comparison of LLT sensors Z-resolution

Laser Line Triangulation Sensor	UNIVPM	Wenglor MLWL2 x4	Wenglor MLWL2 x5	LMI Gocator 2880
Resolution along Z axis [mm]	0.017-0.043	0.039-0.289	0.092-0.439	0.092 - 0.488

B. Measurement setup for Inline Data Acquisition

The overall LLT system is represented in Figure III-5 where the system is completely mounted considering the camera enclosure (top of the tube) and the laser enclosure (bottom of the tube). Enclosures are used to protect camera and laser in the harsh inline environment.

The system has been mounted on a tripod and installed for a feasibility test inline in the VDL Weweler B.V. production plant. The reference system, highlighted in Figure III-5, shows that: the X-axis is along the length of the bar and the Z-axis is along the optical axis of the laser beam.

Figure III-5 Laser Line Triangulation Sensor developed by UNIVPM installed inline for feasibility tests

The measurement sequence is the following:

- The product is picked up by a robot with magnetic grippers and positioned in front of the Laser Line Triangulation sensor. The laser line is projected towards the steel bar in its central part as it can be seen from Figure III-6;
- The robot generates a trigger signal directed to the camera which acquires a laser line profile;
- After the measurement, the bar is positioned back in the line by the robot.

Regarding image acquisition triggering, the C5 camera is capable of accepting an Opto-isolated digital input 1 (+5V to +24V DC) [9] which can be used for the purpose. The trigger

signal generated by the robot is a 24 V gate signal with time duration of 1 s. There are different options for Frame Triggering; in the feasibility test presented in the paper, the Mode *Trigger one frame over camera input 1* is chosen which means a single frame acquisition is triggered over the rising edge of camera input 1. Therefore, when the PLC of the robot generates the gate signal, one frame acquisition is triggered. In each frame it is possible to pack multiple laser line profiles, directly computed when the C5 camera works in 3D Mode. In the use case, for each frame, 30 laser line profiles are acquired at maximum camera speed which is 340 Hz.

Figure III-6 Laser line projected to the steel bar

C. Laser line profile extraction algorithm

The camera AT C5-2040-GigE is a smart camera capable of processing on-board laser-line extraction algorithms. During the acquisition inline, the camera is set in 3D Mode, directly computing the laser line profile, thus saving also memory and computational time.

Nonetheless, before starting the inline continuous acquisition, a phase of tuning of the optical parameters is necessary to obtain good image quality. In Figure III-7 it is presented an image acquired inline while the laser line profile is projected onto the bar to be inspected. The laser line is clearly visible thanks to the presence, in front of the optics, of a narrow band-pass interferential filter at 660 nm, which is the same wavelength as the laser line projector. The filter mostly removes the background, which is also enhanced by low aperture of the diaphragm.

Figure III-7 Image acquisition to set the optical parameters

The intensity profile along the line in red in Figure III-7, which is the pixel 1042 in the middle part of the bar, is shown in Figure III-8. The laser line profile has a sharp peak reaching

a value of 813 intensity, showing the laser line is at focus and not saturated (image is in 10 bit format so saturation is at 1023 intensity value).

Figure III-8 Intensity profile in middle region of the bar

Moreover, the image is at high contrast, reaching a 93% value, calculated with Michelson contrast formula (3) [10], considering this intensity profile (minimum intensity pixel value is 30 and the maximum is 815).

$$\text{Contrast} = \left(\frac{I_{\max} - I_{\min}}{I_{\max} + I_{\min}} \right) * 100 \quad (3)$$

The level of contrast is of primary importance so that the laser line extraction algorithm works properly. Furthermore, the laser line thickness is in the order of 10 pixels, which allows a good performance of subpixel interpolation algorithms.

After setting the optical parameters, a series of laser line profiles has been acquired during full operative mode of the production line.

During the acquisition, the camera directly extracts the laser line profile thanks to the algorithms embedded in the camera processor. Different algorithms can be chosen for the laser line extraction: Maximum Intensity Profile Mode, Threshold Mode, Center Of Gravity Mode, FIR Peak Mode [9]. The one chosen for this use case application is the FIR Peak algorithm, which firstly calculates the first derivative of a Gaussian curve interpolating the laser beam intensity profile. The position of zero-crossing of first derivative is detected and output with subpixel accuracy, and threshold is used to detect the first rising edge of the derived intensity signal, see Figure III-9.

Figure III-9 Laser line extraction algorithm [9]

IV. RESULTS

A. Laser line profiles acquisition on a batch of bars

As the camera is capable of extracting directly the laser line profiles from the image for each bar, triggered by the robot, a series of 30 profiles is acquired on each bar at maximum camera speed which is 340 Hz. For each bar, the average profile is then computed, in order to remove random noise and obtain a clean laser line profile.

A series of average profiles acquired on 180 bars is reported in Figure IV-1.

Figure IV-1 Data acquisition for a batch of bars

As it can be seen from Figure IV-1 the Z measurement units are pixels because, during the inline feasibility tests, the system was not calibrated. A calibration procedure has been developed and is under deployment. Due to the missing calibration, all profiles appear curved; this is not due to the fact that steel bars were curved, it is an artifact caused by the missing calibration.

However, these data allow to extract important information, for example that not all the bars are in the same position. This depends on the fact that, when the robot picks up the bar with the magnetic grippers from the pallet, the bar position is not accurate. Therefore, before processing, each bar profile has to be roto-translated and aligned to the

others. This is achieved by applying a detrending algorithm, so that all bars will be approximately aligned along the X-axis.

B. Data processing and feature extraction

The raw data is processed after the acquisition to extract useful geometric features for the product. For this use case the feature extracted is the bar straightness value.

The algorithm follows these main steps:

- Outliers are removed: some points outside the product are detected, because of ambient interference, and therefore need to be removed;
- The laser line profile is fitted with a polynomial model;
- The fitting data is rotated to be aligned along the X-axis;
- The straightness value is calculated as the maximum deviation of the fitted and detrended laser line profile (line in pink in Figure IV-2) from the straight line. The straight line is calculated as the line passing through the extreme points (aligned along the X-axis, therefore at same Z value) of the profile. The maximum distant point from this line is highlighted with a red dot in Figure IV-2.

Figure IV-2 Straightness measurement

The straightness value is a meaningful feature which can help preventing defect propagation along the production line. Non-straight bars are in fact cause of bending, while the bar overcomes steps like heating and/or rolling. This ends up in a final product which becomes scrap, as the most important mechanical dimensions do not respect the geometrical tolerances required. The straightness is mostly meaningful if measured in the XZ plane (straightness over width) but

Figure IV-3 Residual Analysis

calculating the straightness over thickness (on the XY plane) could be also useful. This can be done rotating the bar on its longer axis and measuring two laser line profiles. The combination of the straightness on the two measurements can be used to estimate torsion of the bar.

C. Residual Analysis of the fitting

To evaluate the quality of the polynomial fit, the residuals can be used as an index. Figure IV-3 shows a polynomial fitting applied to a laser line profile along with the plot of the residuals of the fitting. The residuals show mean value of zero and low standard deviation. Moreover, the histogram distribution shows a gaussian profile, assuring that the polynomial fitting applied to the data is adequate.

However, for some products, a polynomial fitting of second order is not sufficient (see Figure IV-4, a) showing a non-random distribution of the residuals. In that case a higher order of the polynomial fitting is required to obtain a good gaussian distribution in the residuals histogram (see Figure IV-4, b). This proves that the deterministic error has been removed and the residuals show a random distribution as expected, as they are only related to random noise. The histogram of the distribution and the related gaussian fit (in red) shown in Figure IV-4 demonstrate that with the 6th order polynomial fit the standard deviation of the residuals is lower (0.0030 against 0.0037 obtained when a 2nd order polynomial fit is applied). It is common to find experimentally that, regarding residuals from a fitting, large values of random error occur less frequently than small values [11], therefore higher order of polynomial fit with lower standard deviation better represent the usual randomness of residuals.

Figure IV-4 Polynomial fitting of order 2nd (a) and 6th (b) order applied to the same laser line profile

Using higher order polynomial fitting allows also to find a point of maximum deviation from straightness positioned at different x coordinate of the laser line profile. This better suits the case of products which are not only bent in one direction but present more complex shapes like tapering, pincushion or torsion deformations.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

This paper has presented the design and implementation of a Laser Line Triangulation sensor, having a large measurement range and a small resolution. The LLT sensor has been tested inline for a feasibility test. Even though it was not calibrated, the acquired data will serve to optimize the project parameters and tune them for a full inline installation.

The comparison with other existing systems on the market shows that the laser line sensor developed by UNIVPM

features a good compromise of wide measurement range and small resolution along Z axis, down to 0.026 mm, obtainable with subpixel accuracy, at the stand-off distance of 1000 mm over a transversal range of about 1200 mm. This is an optimized condition compared to the 0.83 mm accuracy without sub-pixeling.

The description of the temporary inline installation highlights the main points to take into account and improve, both from hardware and software point of view, in order to develop a fast and precise quality control station.

The next step of the project mainly focuses on the calibration of the sensor which will be implemented using a referenced target with direct calibration procedure. Moreover, lot of other elements can be taken into account to optimize the acquisition and processing software. For example, the straightness value of the bars might be calculated at different heights of the bar, which can be useful for the estimation, not only of the bar straightness, but also its torsion.

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